

Multimedia Educational Resources in Teaching the Professional Language of the Textile Industry

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Abstract. The article examines theoretical and practical aspects of using multimedia educational resources in teaching the professional language of the textile industry. Modern digital and interactive learning tools, their linguistic and methodological potential, and their impact on the formation of terminological and professional communicative competence of learners are analyzed. Based on the conducted analysis, the high effectiveness of multimedia technologies in the system of language education is substantiated.

Keywords: multimedia resources, professional language, textile terminology, interactive methods, digital technologies, language education.

Main Text. In the context of globalization and digitalization of the educational environment, the implementation of innovative pedagogical technologies in teaching professionally oriented disciplines is becoming increasingly important [1.: 256.]. One of the promising directions of modern language education is the use of multimedia educational resources that ensure the integration of traditional and digital forms of learning.

The professional language of the textile industry represents a complex system of specialized terms reflecting technological processes, types of raw materials, equipment, and finished products [2.: 312.]. Mastering this terminology requires a comprehensive approach, as many terms are characterized by a high degree of abstraction and cross-linguistic variability. In this regard, multimedia resources serve as an effective tool for visualization and contextualization of terminological material [3.: 180.].

Among the most востребованные multimedia tools are electronic textbooks, interactive presentations, instructional videos, digital terminological

databases, and online platforms [4.: 145.; 5.: 304.]. The use of video materials demonstrating real production processes (spinning, weaving, dyeing, and finishing of fabrics) contributes to the formation of stable associative links between the term and the concept it denotes [6.: 57.].

From a linguistic perspective, multimedia educational resources provide multimodal perception of information by combining textual, visual, and audio components. This is particularly important when teaching professional vocabulary, as it contributes to a deeper understanding of term semantics and reduces the likelihood of interference in cross-linguistic translation [7.: 246.].

The methodological basis of the research included methods of scientific and methodological literature analysis, pedagogical observation, and comparative analysis of traditional and multimedia forms of teaching. The study established that the systematic use of multimedia resources increases learners' motivation, activates their cognitive activity, and contributes to the development of professional language competence.

Multimedia technologies are of particular importance in the formation of translation skills, as they allow consideration of cross-linguistic equivalence of terms and the specifics of their functioning in professional texts. Digital glossaries and interactive exercises create conditions for practical mastering of terminology in various communicative situations [8.: 271.].

The obtained results confirm the feasibility of integrating multimedia educational resources into teaching the professional language of the textile industry. The use of digital technologies ensures a higher level of mastering terminological material and contributes to training competitive specialists capable of effectively functioning in modern production conditions.

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